

An Integrated Digital Twin Architecture for Water Contamination Emergency Management

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ABSTRACT

During emergencies such as floods or earthquakes, first responders, water authorities, and public health experts must collaborate to manage water contamination risks. Decision-support tools, such as Digital Twins are critical for real-time risk assessment and the evaluation of response measures within limited timeframes. Digital Twins integrate real-time sensor data and dynamic models, along with algorithms for state estimation, to support risk assessment, anomaly detection, and event management. However, a holistic framework for water contamination emergency response is currently lacking. We introduce a novel, integrated Digital Twin reference architecture for risk-based water contamination emergency management, built on insights from various European research and innovation projects. This architecture integrates multiple water systems (surface, urban, sewerage), wastewater surveillance, public health and open data, portable sensors, emergency data spaces, simulation tools to forecast incident evolution, and time-bounded algorithms for event diagnosis, co-simulation, and risk assessment. A realistic use case is presented based on a large-scale field exercise.

INTRODUCTION

Emergency water pathogen contamination events present a significant risk to drinking water distribution, public health, and the environment. These events are occurring globally due to several factors, including natural disasters such as earthquakes, and other events like floods, which may be exacerbated by climate change. Drinking water can be contaminated under certain conditions due to wastewater or industrial chemical infiltration, inadequate disinfection, accidents causing cascading events leading to contamination, and even deliberate attacks on

water infrastructure. The impact of these events can be severe, ranging from public health emergencies to economic and social disruption, as well as environmental pollution.

During the past years, various contamination events have occurred worldwide. In 2015, sewage water leaked from a Prague military hospital, infiltrating Dejvice's drinking water network. In 2020, a fire in an Italian town led to infections due to cross-contamination with a fire truck water tank, which was already contaminated. The following year, an earthquake in central Greece caused soil infiltration into boreholes used for the supply of water to a city, eventually spreading the contamination throughout the distribution system. A cyberattack at a Florida treatment plant put water safety at risk by elevating sodium hydroxide levels. Catastrophic floods in Germany heightened infection risks by mixing drinking water with wastewater, and in 2022, a cholera outbreak in Lebanon was traced to water pollution. The recent catastrophic earthquake in Turkey and Syria, as well as the unprecedented floods in Greece and Spain, underscored the ongoing risk of waterborne diseases after a crisis.

The urgency of these situations demands the development and implementation of effective emergency response technologies to minimize the impact of contamination events. During such emergencies, multiple stakeholders may be involved, such as first responders in the field and local command and control centers, public health experts and microbiologists, water operators, representatives from different agencies and local government at joint coordination centers, as well as volunteers and citizens. The challenge, therefore, lies in providing timely, scientifically valid recommendations and risk estimations as the event unfolds and while the situation awareness is still limited. For instance, during a possible drinking water contamination emergency, the incident commander may pose the following questions to the water authority and public health experts:

- What is the risk of an emergency event (such as a flood) cascading to the drinking water supply?
- Which areas in the city are at risk of not having access to safe water?
- Which are the possible sources of contamination, and what are the risks to human health?
- What is the number of people expected to be affected and infected, thus requiring medical assistance during the next 2, 4, 8, and 12 hours?

To give appropriate answers to such questions, water operators and public health experts need to jointly assess the risks, assisted by digital tools capable of fusing different types of information from the field, as well as information from Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and seamlessly integrated Internet of Things (IoT) sensors. A holistic solution requires the development of real-time computational models of the subject systems and processes, usually referred to as “Digital Twins,” that can be coupled with decision-making tools to help responders manage these events with better information, more timely and more effectively.

In this paper, we introduce an integrated Digital Twin architecture for assisting first responders, water operators, public health authorities, and criminal investigators in mitigating from, preparing for, responding to, and recovering from water contamination events, as summarized in Figure 1. For example, Digital Twins can be used during full-scale, tabletop, or simulation exercises for preparedness. They can help implement, in an optimal way, monitoring systems that reduce the risk of high-impact events going undetected. They can also help identify the extent of the event after it has occurred and its source. Additionally, they can assess the risk

and forecast the evolution of the event, evaluate the impact of different response actions, and also facilitate the post-event analysis, including their use as evidence in criminal investigations.

Figure 1. The different stages of water contamination emergency management

The contributions of this work are:

1. Introducing a reference architecture and the requirements for the implementation of a digital twin focused on water contamination emergencies.
2. Present a case-study simulation of a flood which causes a contamination event due to wastewater infiltration to a borehole.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides background on the concept of Digital Twins and how they can be used for emergency situations. Section 3 introduces the proposed integrated architecture. Section 4 presents a realistic case study highlighting the different elements of the proposed architecture and discusses the application of the framework. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper and introduces future challenges.

BACKGROUND ON DIGITAL TWINS FOR EMERGENCY MANAGEMENT

The concept of Digital Twins was first introduced in 2002, envisioning a physical system continuously communicating data to its virtual counterpart, which, in turn, feeds information back to the physical system (Grieves & Vickers, 2017). The concept was initially geared towards Product Lifecycle Management, and has since expanded to a wider range of applications. NASA popularized Digital Twins as high-fidelity simulations integrated with real and historical data of a physical system to enhance safety and reliability (Glaessgen & Stargel, 2012). A crucial element of Digital Twins is the use of models and simulations for exploring “what-if” scenarios, which are pertinent to monitoring, control, diagnostics, and prediction (Lu et al., 2020). A definition relevant to Smart Water Networks, as proposed by Rasheed et al. (2020), describes Digital Twins as virtual representations of physical systems enabled through data and simulators for real-time prediction, optimization, monitoring, control, and enhanced decision-making. Several papers (e.g., Tao et al., 2018; Tao et al., 2019; Jones et al., 2020; Kritzinger et al., 2018; Zheng et al., 2019; Cheng et al., 2023) have summarized the main characteristics of Digital Twins and their application to various fields, including manufacturing, healthcare, energy, transportation, smart cities, aerospace, and others.

In the context of emergency events, various research groups have investigated the application of Digital Twins for enhancing situational awareness and decision-making, improving emergency response and coordination, predicting and mitigating risks, and supporting recovery. For example, Digital Twins have been studied for city-level disaster management (Fan et al., 2021;

Ford & Wolf, 2020; Wolf et al., 2022), including applications for floods (Ghaith et al., 2021) and earthquakes (Yu et al., 2023). They have also been used to forecast the evolution of events, such as the spread of a plume (Shi et al., 2021), and to evaluate the impact on public health, such as hospitalizations after an earthquake (Basaglia et al., 2022). At a larger scale, Digital Twins are being used for extremely large-scale systems, such as Earth's climate under the Destination Earth initiative (Bauer et al., 2021) and oceans under the European Digital Twin Ocean initiative (Tzachor et al., 2023).

Digital Twins have also been considered in smart water systems research. These systems integrate smart sensors and actuators into water networks, with advanced Information and Communication Technologies, IoT, and Data Spaces for managing and exchanging data. These data are combined through the Digital Twin with computational and machine learning models for short- and long-term decision-making, optimization, and control. Water systems Digital Twins have been used to study leakage and pressure management (Ramos et al., 2022), hydraulic and quality fault detection (Baena-Miret et al., 2024), and other applications.

As part of the EU-funded project *Pathogen Contamination Emergency Response Technologies* (PathoCERT), an innovative Digital Twin was developed for evaluating different scenarios and the impact of contamination events within drinking water distribution systems (Paraskevopoulos et al., 2022). This Digital Twin modeled the health impacts using a quantitative risk-based approach (Paraskevopoulos et al., 2024). The tool was evaluated in full-scale emergency exercises in Spain (Granada), Cyprus (Limassol), Greece (Thessaloniki), and Bulgaria (Sofia), as well as in tabletop exercises in the Netherlands (Amsterdam). Based on this experience, gaps and requirements were identified for the future design of Digital Twins for Water Contamination Emergency Management, and are presented in the following section.

INTEGRATED DIGITAL TWIN ARCHITECTURE

The proposed integrated Digital Twin architecture is depicted graphically in Figure 2. The basic components of the architecture include: 1) the *Data Spaces* (gray), 2) the *Data Processing and Backend Module* (green), 3) the *State Estimation and Model Learning Module* (purple), 4) the *Application Module* (cyan), 5) the *Computational Infrastructure* (orange), 6) the *External Digital Twins* (blue), and 7) the high-level *User Services Modules* (red). In the following paragraphs, we detail each module and further discuss its importance during water contamination emergency response.

Data Spaces: The concept of Data Spaces has gained significant attention in recent years as a term that encompasses various aspects related to data management, data engineering, and data sharing, among others (Curry et al., 2022). The need for Data Spaces has been recognized in the EU's Data Act (COM/2022/68 final), which establishes a legal framework for organizations within the EU to share data. Particularly in emergency situations, such as floods or earthquakes, businesses are obligated to provide certain data needed to address the emergency and improve evidence-based decision-making by the government. In practice, Data Spaces may utilize a Data Space Connector, essentially a communication server for sending and receiving data in compliance with widely adopted standards for data sharing (e.g., the SmartWater Data Model). Information models (e.g., NGS-ILD) and domain-specific ontologies can be employed to capture the metadata of the shared data.

In the context of contamination emergency management, we consider three different types of Data Spaces: External, Internal, and Emergency Data Spaces:

Figure 2. Architecture of an Integrated Digital Twin Platform.

- a) **External Data Spaces** essentially include all data spaces that are not owned by the water authority. This can include public health data spaces (e.g., hospitalizations with specific symptoms that could be used to detect issues in water quality), governmental data spaces (e.g., demographics, vulnerable groups, etc.), satellite data spaces (e.g., Sentinel-2 data through the European Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem), and open governmental data (e.g., buildings, geographical information, elevations, environmental sensors, meteorological data, etc.). In addition, Data Spaces of other critical infrastructure systems can provide important information during an emergency: electric power failures can affect the operation of pumps, telecommunication disruptions can interfere with the transmission of telemetry and SCADA operations, and failures in other water-related infrastructures can increase the risk of events in the drinking water system.
- b) **Internal Data Spaces** include all the information collected by the water authority, providing unified access to data related to SCADA and telemetry, GIS, customer profiles, maintenance records, call centers (which may receive water quality complaints during an emergency), and smart meters (which can be programmed to send data in near real-time for rapid state estimation). They also include nominal hydraulic and quality models, which can later be updated as new information arrives from the monitoring of the physical system.
- c) **Emergency Data Spaces** comprise an obligation within the context of the new European Data Act. These can be established on an ad-hoc basis driven by the actual needs (even in an *ad hoc* basis), depending on the specific emergency, in contrast to the first two, which may be in place well before the occurrence of an event. Emergency Data Spaces can include data from newly installed IoT sensors for monitoring various parameters (e.g., radioactivity, pathogens, etc.), video feeds from drones, rapid test results, smart cameras (e.g., for detecting turbidity in lakes), wastewater surveillance (Karaolia et al., 2024), as well as other information for First and Second Responders, as well as data shared by volunteers and bystanders.

Data Processing and Backend Module: The backend should be able to easily connect and add new data sources from the different Data Spaces, especially when Emergency Data Spaces are activated. Data received through the Data Spaces can be processed through streaming analytics to extract important information, produce alerts, or configure the metadata of the measurements in accordance with specific Data Models. This can occur in real time or via batch processing to balance the load on the databases and servers, which could be critical during an emergency. The backend module orchestrates communication between the different elements of the Digital Twin and ensures that authorized applications receive the required information within a certain timeframe.

Computational Infrastructure: During an emergency, many requests for executing applications need to be treated as time-critical. It is, therefore, important to design the backend and the task manager in a way that can handle requests with different computational requirements and effectively utilize the available computational infrastructure. The computational infrastructure that is called upon can be located on different servers with varying capabilities and loads. Typically, dedicated application servers (or virtualizations within the application servers) are used, which can, in turn, be connected to GPU servers, especially when machine learning algorithms need to be executed within the application.

Depending on the scale of the emergency event, small-scale CPU/GPU servers may not be sufficient for executing certain applications. For example, running a large-scale Monte Carlo Simulation to evaluate the risk across all possible contamination scenarios within a large water distribution network may exceed the capacity of smaller systems. This type of computation can be easily parallelized on a High-Performance Computer (HPC). Moreover, the “urgent computing” paradigm is also supported by HPC infrastructure, allowing the execution of time-critical computations during emergencies (Beckman et al., 2007).

External Digital Twins: The different modules may require and request additional information from interconnected systems, which is not covered by the Data Spaces. This includes forecasts and estimates based on external Digital Twin services. For instance, an early warning module may request, from *Destination Earth* (the large-scale climate Digital Twin), a high-resolution forecast of weather conditions in a critical area of the emergency. Additionally, the Digital Twin Oceans can be used to assess whether a marine contamination incident will affect the area around a critical desalination plant. Finally, as mentioned, other water systems could impact the drinking water supply. For example, a request could be made to an external Digital Twin specializing in forecasting river flow and estimating the risk of flooding at a specific location.

State Estimation and Model Learning Module: For the Digital Twins to be fully utilized, various other tools and technologies must be available. From a control-systems perspective, state estimation is a critical component of Digital Twins, enabling the estimation of unknown states in the system that are not measured by SCADA or IoT sensors (Vrachimis et al., 2019; Vrachimis et al., 2021). Computational models are essential for simulating the dynamics of water contamination. In practice, these can include EPANET (Rossman, 2000) for hydraulics and EPANET-MSX models (Shang et al., 2008) for water quality. Moreover, machine learning can be used to learn the dynamics of parts of the system that cannot be modeled from first principles of mathematics or computationally, as well as to continuously update the system parameters through learning (Farrell & Polycaprou, 2006; Kyrkou et al., 2022; Eliades et al., 2014; Malialis et al., 2022). Lastly, Data Models provide a common language for the data, based on shared ontologies and data structures (Sweetapple et al., 2022).

Applications Module: In the context of smart water systems, a wide range of decision support tools have been developed, addressing all the emergency response stages in Figure 1 (Eliades et al., 2023). These methodologies can be integrated with simulation engines, e.g., using EPyT/EPyT-FLOW (Kyriakou et al., 2023; Artelt et al., 2024), WNTR (Klise et al., 2018), etc. Example methodologies include estimating the public health risk of a possible contamination event (e.g., wastewater infiltration), creating maps of the evolution of a contamination event over the next few hours, assessing the impact with respect to the number of people affected (to account for additional water supply needs), and estimating the number of people hospitalized. The list of possible applications is continuously expanding with new research results. An important aspect of this proposed architecture is the identification of key requirements. As mentioned earlier, a critical aspect is that these methodologies are time-sensitive, meaning they must be able to produce timely results in accordance with the requirements of the incident management procedure.

Moreover, these methodologies should be designed to execute on the available Computational Infrastructure, which may include High-Performance Computing (HPC). For this purpose, workflows can be employed to define how the different algorithms are executed, depending on the availability of data, time constraints, and other factors. Another critical aspect of the workflow component is the ability to reconfigure algorithms if some data are missing or become corrupted during an emergency.

Moreover, Knowledge Bases with various facts should be accessible to the different methodologies. For instance, these Knowledge Bases may include parameters and reaction dynamics of different pathogens, kinetics from the scientific literature, and other information organized in the form of ontologies.

User Services Modules: This is the layer of the Digital Twin that interacts with users and other services. An Incident Management System (IMS) is typically an information system operated by first and second responders to coordinate the various missions executed by different teams. Various types of information generated by the Digital Twin can be used. For instance, “hot zones” can inform responders to avoid using contaminated water or help in setting up first-aid stations. The Risk Assessment and Early Warning System may be an application that operates continuously, analyzing available sensor data and executing forecasting scenarios within the Digital Twin to estimate public health risks in real time. For example, the trajectory of a storm can be analyzed to assess which infrastructure might fail. New alerts and information arriving in this system from the IMS can also be processed to evaluate their risk. Establishing a common GIS for situational awareness is critical when multiple agencies are involved. Typically, this is a passive system that aggregates and visualizes critical information on a map, enabling the Incident Commander to make informed decisions.

Finally, the Decision Support System is an advanced system that allows specialized personnel to assess risks and answer questions posed by the Incident Commander. By analyzing information arriving from different data sources, the Risk Assessment team operating the Decision Support System can request the execution of specific applications, process the results, and communicate them back to the relevant stakeholders.

CASE STUDY & DISCUSSION

In the following, we present an illustrative case-study scenario and discuss its implications with respect to the proposed architecture. In this scenario, a high-intensity storm is expected to affect the area of Yermasogia in Limassol (Figure 3) within the next 6 hours, with a high risk of reservoir overflow and possible flooding. This scenario is adapted from an actual Full-Scale Exercise conducted on September 21, 2023, in Limassol, Cyprus, within the framework of PathoCERT¹.

Figure 3. The Yermasogia area in Limassol (reservoir and aquifer).

Description of the pilot area: The reservoir in Yermasogia receives water from two rivers, and its water is released in a controlled way through a stream to enrich the downstream aquifer. The water authorities maintain boreholes in the aquifer, which serve as the main source of potable water in Yermasogia. Due to its proximity to the city, various critical infrastructures are also present in the area, intersecting the downstream flow of the stream. These include wastewater infrastructure, power system infrastructure, transportation infrastructure, several buildings, and small businesses.

Implementation: The scenario is demonstrated on the OCEANOS Digital Twin, which is currently being developed for the Limassol District Local Government Organization. In accordance with the reference architecture, the OCEANOS Digital Twin (depicted in Figure 4) is a high-level User Service Module. It is a custom QGIS plugin, where the internal and external data layers are on the right-hand side, and the computational models and the applications are on the left-hand side. The middle section depicts the selected layers, such as the drinking water and wastewater networks, as well as the buildings.

For the **Data Spaces**, in accordance with the proposed architecture, we established connectors to different internal data sources (SCADA, IoT Platforms, GIS, Maintenance, Call Center, etc.). Additionally, we established connectors with various external data sources to receive time-series data, either in batch or real time, such as daily Yermasogia reservoir levels, data related to power, telecommunication, and transportation network infrastructure, demographic data, metadata of building infrastructures, meteorological forecasts, and more. In principle, relevant open data from national or European Data Spaces should be made accessible through the Digital Twin.

¹ A video summarizing the exercise is available at: https://youtu.be/fk_Z-uUdxgU

For the **Data Processing and Backend Module**, a Python-based backend was implemented to process and store the retrieved data in a dedicated database. This database is used locally by the different applications and provides an API for direct access to the data in a unified way. Moreover, this module uses a task queue (Celery) and a message broker (RabbitMQ) to manage requests and their execution by different workers.

The **Applications Module** is comprised of various “smart apps” that can be executed on the operator’s device or on a separate computational infrastructure residing on a dedicated application server, depending on the complexity.

Lastly, the **State Estimation and Model Learning Module** is comprised of computational models of hydraulic dynamics, which are automatically generated from the OCEANOS GIS platform and calibrated based on relevant sensor data (e.g., inflows, pressure sensors, etc.).

Figure 4. The OCEANOS Digital Twin Decision Support System

Yermasogia Flood Scenario: To evaluate the risks from a potential overflow, the operator can select the “Flooding” app, which is already available in the Applications Module. The application allows the user to specify the amount of rainfall expected within the next 3 hours, as provided by the meteorological services. By combining this information with the reservoir geometry and the latest water levels, the app computes the risk of an overflow and estimates the level of the overflow. In this scenario, a 1-in-20-year flood event is likely to occur within the next few hours, and pre-calculated flood risk maps are already stored in the knowledge base. Note: if new maps were required, a new task could have been executed on a dedicated application server.

As seen in Figure 5, the area at risk of flooding (red area) is physically associated with various infrastructures (power, wastewater, drinking water, transportation, buildings, etc.). Fragility curves can be employed, for example, to evaluate the effect of the storm or flood on power pillars and assess the likelihood of asset failure (Panteli et al., 2016).

From a water contamination point of view, the critical issue is that the application identified nine sewerage manholes in the path of the expected flood. As a result, the potential flood may

cause sewage overflow, posing a risk of contaminating the boreholes (indicated as reservoirs in Figure 5) that supply clean water to the nearby tanks.

Figure 5. Possible flooded area and affected infrastructure.

To further investigate the contamination risk of such an event, the operator executes the “Run Scenarios” application (Figure 6). This application runs a series of algorithms to estimate the contamination risk. From the knowledge base, a list of possible pathogens is extracted (e.g., Cryptosporidium), along with expected concentration values derived from past emergencies. The EPANET model of the network downstream from the affected borehole (as identified in Figure 7a) is calibrated based on the latest flow, smart meters, and pressure measurements from the internal Data Space using a state-estimation algorithm, which computes the actual node demands and forecasts consumption for the next 24 hours. Moreover, an EPANET-MSX model is updated based on sensor measurements (e.g., chlorine, TOC) and pathogen estimates from the knowledge base. The result is a map that animates the contamination evolution over time (Figure 7b) and an Impact Assessment table, which computes the percentage of affected people within this network. This calculation considers the demographics and the allocation of consumers to each node, using data from both External and Internal Data Spaces.

Figure 6. The "Run Scenarios", for forecasting the evolution of the contamination event and compute the impact with and without interventions.

Figure 7. Simulating wastewater contamination infiltration into the drinking water system.

Table 1 summarizes the contamination impact risk, i.e., the percentage of people affected by the contamination event at different time instances if there is no intervention. The operator can also evaluate different interventions, such as closing some valves in the network, and comparing their impact on the event. In this case, the operator evaluates the closure of three valves in the network.

Table 1. Contamination Impact Risk without and with intervention

Contamination Impact Risk	05:00	10:00	15:00	20:00
No intervention	0%	36%	78%	95%
With intervention	0%	36%	52%	52%

Discussion: Even though the case study provides a realistic proof-of-concept for the proposed architecture, it is not a complete implementation, as it requires the integration of multiple advanced technologies and possibly the adoption of new policies at a national level. Specifically, the establishment of Data Spaces will be a requirement for effectively implementing the new European Data Act. However, very few initiatives are currently in progress within the water domain (e.g., the HEU WATERVERSE Project).

In general, data management and sharing are critical challenges, and significant changes are required to establish, in addition to the normal Data Spaces, Emergency Data Spaces for sharing critical data relevant to an ongoing crisis as it evolves in time and space. Furthermore, during the H2020 PathoCERT pilots, it was suggested by the operators that backend platforms need to be continuously active and integrated into normal system operations. This would also enable the maintenance of reasonably accurate computational models.

It should be noted, however, that during an emergency, the system may change (e.g., after an earthquake, part of the network may be destroyed), requiring the construction of an updated model. Handling uncertainties is another critical challenge, as the system may not have been preconfigured for certain events. For this reason, the Digital Twin and its applications should provide flexibility in creating workflows as needed to answer specific questions posed by the Incident Commander.

Another important aspect is to consider bounds in the state estimation and forecasts, if possible, to better capture uncertainties in system topology, dynamics, and risk. Finally, continuous training is required to effectively use these tools during emergencies. For this reason, frequent Full-Scale, Tabletop, or Simulation Exercises are needed, involving multiple stakeholders.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This paper introduces a comprehensive integrated digital twin architecture for water contamination emergency management. In contrast to digital twins for operational purposes, emergency management requires communication with external stakeholders (e.g., first responders), as well as the timely response to assess the risk and impact of an event expected to happen in the near future, generate maps, identify the source of the event, and, in general, provide quantitative insights to support ongoing emergency response missions. The proposed framework integrates advanced technologies, such as Data Spaces, with Digital Twins and identifies critical components of the Digital Twins in relation to state estimation and model learning, the development of applications, execution on computational infrastructure (including HPC), as well as connection to other Digital Twins.

Future work needs to address a wide range of challenges: 1) directly incorporating distributed computing frameworks to handle large-scale and complex computations, 2) considering how the system needs to be reconfigured in the case of a digital breakdown, 3) incorporating and quantifying uncertainties in the applications, 4) developing standardized ontologies to be adopted by water authorities during emergencies, 5) developing machine learning models that can be shared between organizations for predicting the evolution of contamination scenarios, 6) aligning the proposed framework to comply with the European AI, Data, and Critical Entities Resilience Acts, 7) conducting regular training through simulation exercises to enhance preparedness, and 8) improving the usability and accessibility of the Digital Twin and the way its results are communicated to water authorities, first responders, and other stakeholders.

Through the adoption of Digital Twins for contamination emergency management, we envisage that water operators will be equipped with a powerful tool to support first responders by providing real-time, data-driven insights, improving situational awareness, and reducing the impact of emergencies, thereby contributing to more resilient societies in the face of future crises.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

MP, DE, SV, CP, and CL: Part of their work was co-funded under the European Research Council (ERC) Synergy Grant Agreement No. 951424 (Water-Futures), the European Union Horizon 2020 programme Grant Agreement No. 739551 (KIOS CoE), and the Government of the Republic of Cyprus through the Deputy Ministry of Research, Innovation, and Digital Policy.

DK, MK: Part of their work was co-funded under Horizon Europe Grant Agreements No. 101081728 (IntoDBP) and No. 101157371 (IDEATION).

GM: Part of his work was co-funded under the European Regional Development Fund through the Research and Innovation Foundation Grant Agreement ENTERPRISES/0521/0081 (DigiWATER) and the Horizon Europe programme Grant Agreement No. 101070262 (Waterverse).

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